

مركز قيادة
قوات السلطان المسلحة

HEAD QUARTERS
SULTAN'S ARMED FORCES
P.O. Box 602, MUSCAT,

OMAN

06 Oct 72

Dear Andrew,

Thank-you very much for your letter of 18th September. I'm sorry to be so late in answering it but I was away from home until the day before I left to come here and so I'm afraid I missed the opportunity to contact you before leaving. This is a pity as I could have given you the full and rather involved situation here. However I'll endeavour to summarise it in this letter.

The Oman Historical Association was formed at the end of last year under the energetic direction of a civil engineer. Its aim is to protect Oman's historical buildings and archaeological sites from the ravages of development (which is progressing at an alarming rate) and to gather as much information as possible so that professionals can come and survey and dig. We are entirely amateur and vary between those who are deeply interested in specific fields and those who enjoy picnic trips to places of interest. As an association we have virtually no funds. Unfortunately the founder left in July and we have not found a replacement ^{with} his drive and energy, so some of the momentum has been lost. I was offered the job but ~~could not~~ did not feel I could do it properly because of other commitments here which

fill just about every minute of one's ^{spare} leisure.

The President of the Association is ex-officio the Director General of Information an Omani member of Government. He is also responsible for Tourism and will when the body is eventually formed ~~to~~ be responsible for antiquities. It is in this field that funds may become available, especially if they can be justified by future tourist potential. One government project is to set up a Museum but the building earmarked is not yet available (it is currently occupied by the Ministry of Economy, who, in our present climate, must have first call!). It may be available towards the end of next year.

Please regard this paragraph as strictly confidential. A certain SAF officer, a most distinguished chap who has served us long and well, is due to retire this autumn. He has been offered, subject to confirmation that accommodation is available, the job with the Government as curator of the projected Museum, although the job has not yet been clearly defined. He is very knowledgeable on certain periods of Oman's more recent history, but is not qualified in any way. There has been a strong lobby by a high-powered chap in the committee of the Historical Association to get a properly qualified person to do the job instead of him. We may have reached the point of no return but the machinations in this part of the world are such that it is not necessarily a fait accompli. The proposed alternative is that we

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should advertise for and "properly" select a properly qualified person. I am not sure but I believe the salary suggested for the job offer was of the order of £2600 p.a. with free accommodation in Muscat. This would not necessarily apply to the job if it were offered to the world at large. It might be more or less. This figure is however high by government standards here but low by SAF standards. The cost of living is high generally, but there is no income tax.

It was in this context that I discussed the matter with David Stronach and it would appear that you would be the ideal person to do this job. However I am not optimistic that we can alter the present state of affairs. I am now doing what I can in the right quarter and I hope to be in a position to let you know whether or not the possibility still exists within the next month or so. The time scale you mentioned would be much more suitable to us than the present plan, which would give us a curator nearly a year ahead of a museum for him to work in.

Until the Coup of July 1970 this country had no government and no education; hence the machinery is very limited still. However we find it all a most stimulating environment to work in as there is so much good to be done in whatever direction we choose to turn.

As far as all this is concerned I have no executive power whatsoever. I deputise for the Vice President as the SAF member of the Historical Association Committee when he is unable to attend. However any decisions concerning visits or expenditure

have to be made by the Directa General
of bifurcation and cannot be made by
the Association.

Even discounting the other possibility
I feel that a visit by you here would
be of great value to us, but I doubt
whether funds would be available to help you.
If you were able to come at your own
expense, I am sure we would have
no difficulty in getting clearance. Accommodation
is a severe problem. We only have one hotel
(near Muscat) and it is exorbitantly expensive.
Elsewhere the choice is between camping,
staying in primitive local accommodation
(which I do quite regularly and happily)
and staying in the nearest military
messes. If you were able to write a
report on your visit for us I'm quite sure
that the Government would pay all expenses
out here. However air tickets are expensive.
A monthly return London - Muscat is £196
approximately.

I am sorry to have to harp on the
subject of finance so much, but because of our
war in Dhofar things are very tight indeed.
I really want to give you a frank
picture of the situation to ensure that
your hopes are not raised and dashed
unnecessarily.

I will let you know any developments
in the situation ~~as~~ as soon as they
occur and expect to be able to write to you
within the next month.

Yours sincerely,
David Inall